

TopBrain Segmentation Challenge for Whole Brain Vessel Anatomy: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

TopBrain Segmentation Challenge for Whole Brain Vessel Anatomy

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

TopBrain2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The proposed TopBrain challenge is an extension to the previously held TopCoW challenge [1], as we now extend the vessel annotations from the base of the brain to the whole brain vessel anatomy. For the past two MICCAI conferences from 2023 to 2024, the TopCoW challenge was successfully organized with positive responses. It was the first large annotated dataset and benchmark for multi-class segmentation of the Circle of Willis (CoW), an important vessel network at the base of the brain. We released to the public 250 angiography scans on two common angiographic modalities, magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) and computed tomography angiography (CTA). Each brain image was annotated voxel-wise with 13 vessel classes of the CoW anatomy. Our two iterations of the TopCoW challenge received more than 360 registrations from participants from six continents. Over 25 teams made high-quality submissions to the benchmark. The best solutions achieved nearly 90% class-average Dice for the CoW segmentation, above 85% intersection-over-union (IoU) for CoW detection, and above 85% class-balanced accuracy for CoW variant classification. The TopCoW challenge was one of the officially featured challenges on the grand-challenge platform, and was at some point with the most submissions. TopCoW arxiv preprint has since been cited by around 20 publications, many of which were accepted into impactful conferences like MICCAI and ECCV.

The positive responses from the TopCoW challenge indicate the interest from the MICCAI community for detailed, accurate, and multi-class segmentation on the complex brain vessel anatomy. The good performances of the submitted algorithms on CoW show potential of the technology to be extended to all vessel anatomy of the brain. Through the TopCoW challenge, our organizers have also established the workflow and expertise to prepare, annotate, and release large datasets with clinically verified and accurate vessel anatomy for brain images. We can build upon the TopCoW challenge to extend the annotation and dataset, from CoW to all the multi-class anatomical vessels in the angiography modalities. Thus we propose to organize such an extension of the TopCoW

challenge that we call the TopBrain challenge.

The TopBrain challenge will continue the benchmark on the CoW, like in the TopCoW challenge, since the CoW is part of the whole brain vessel anatomy. However, the TopBrain challenge will cover much more than the CoW. It includes all the other major artery and vein anatomies of the brain, many of which are equally clinically relevant as the CoW and are of research interest themselves. To name a few: The ophthalmic artery (OA) is relevant to blindness and eye diseases; External carotid arteries (ECA) are important for cerebral bypass surgery; Superior cerebellar artery (SCA) supplies blood to the cerebellum, along with branches along the vertebral artery (VA) and basilar artery (BA) such as the PICA and AICA; Vessels downstream of CoW are also clinically relevant such as the detailed segments of M2, M3 and M4 of the middle cerebral artery (MCA) as they often need to be located down to their section region for stroke treatment; A branch of the ECA called the middle meningeal artery (MMA) is linked to epidural hematoma, but can be often mistaken in other annotations for peripheral vessels of MCA like M4 due to the proximity. The TopBrain challenge will also cover veins of the brain, such as the superior sagittal sinus, basal veins, and the transverse sinus, which are related to venous strokes. The whole brain vessel anatomy, including all major arteries and veins that can be identified in angiography, are annotated and segmented in the TopBrain challenge.

The proposed TopBrain challenge is beneficial to both clinicians and medical imaging researchers. A whole brain vessel anatomy segmentation with anatomical labelings and localizations can be combined with existing models for clinical tasks and applications, such as vessel stenosis or occlusion localization and aneurysm localization. Such a complete anatomy model can also be used in medical report generation and disease management and personalized treatment planning. Based on the clinical impact, data value, and research potential, we look forward to organizing the new TopBrain challenge and are sincerely welcoming submissions.

[1] Yang, K., Musio, F., Ma, Y., Juchler, N., Paetzold, J. C., Al-Maskari, R., ... & Menze, B. (2023). Benchmarking the CoW with the TopCoW Challenge: Topology-Aware Anatomical Segmentation of the Circle of Willis for CTA and MRA. arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.17670.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Brain Vessel Map, Anatomical Segmentation, Brain CT Angiography, Brain MR Angiography

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge will release the first segmentation dataset for voxel-level multi-class annotations of the whole human head vessels. The detailed anatomical classes cover all identifiable major vessels in commonly used angiography modalities of CTA and MRA.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Automatic segmentation of all the major brain vessels of commonly used angiographic modalities like CTA or MRA in task-1 is firstly a key piece in general medical AI. The whole vessel map from the segmentation gives localization information, and can be combined with many existing models on various pathologies. For example, segmentation or detection models for aneurysm, vessel occlusion, stenosis can now be located down to the exact vessel anatomy of the brain.

The TopBrain dataset is also very useful for medical knowledge sharing and medical training. Such detailed brain vessel anatomy often require highly specialized medical experts in neurosurgery.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

TopBrain will combine with Stroke Workshop on Imaging and Treatment CHallenges (SWITCH) workshop for a joint half-day session.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

The tasks proposed are new and quite challenging, thus we would like to have enough time for the community to meet and exchange ideas and solutions.

In addition, TopBrain will organize a joint half-day program with the SWITCH workshop.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect at least 15-20 teams with over 100 registered participants based on the publicity and community carried over from the two years of TopCoW challenge. There has been a growing interest in vessel/topology papers at MICCAI in recent years, which can contribute to a further increase of the participants to TopBrain.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, we plan to summarize and publish the TopBrain challenge results in a journal publication.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

For the in-person event, we need projectors, microphones, loudspeakers, and also a camera/videoconferencing system for hybrid participation.

The challenge will be off-line but hosted on grand-challenge.org. Participants use their own computing resources for the algorithm training and development. The organizers will use grand-challenge.org for the docker evaluation during the testing phase.

TASK 1: Multiclass Segmentation of Whole Brain Vessel Anatomy on CTA and MRA

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Same as the challenge abstract, please see above. Additional points for task-1:

The task is to segment the major and identifiable anatomical vessels from an input brain angiographic 3D image of either CTA or MRA modality. The list of vessels to be segmented is listed in the "Algorithm Target" section.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Same as the challenge keywords, please see above.

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

[University of Zurich, Switzerland]

Kaiyuan Yang, Houjing Huang, Fabio Musio, Ezequiel de la Rosa, Suprosanna Shit, Bjoern Menze

[Harbin Institute of Technology (Shenzhen), China]

Pengcheng Shi

[Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University, China]

Yihui Ma

[EURECOM, France]

Maria A. Zuluaga, Daniele Falchetta

[Department of Radiology at Weill Cornell Medicine, Cornell University, US]

Johannes C. Paetzold

[Department of Radiology, Guy's and St. Thomas NHS Foundation Trust, UK]

[School of Biomedical Engineering and Imaging Sciences, King's College London, UK]

Jon Cleary

[Helmholtz Munich, Germany]

Rami Al-Maskari, Luciano Höher

[University Hospital of Zurich, Switzerland]

Susanne Wegener, Hakim Baazaoui

[German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ) Heidelberg, Germany]

Maximilian R. Rokuss, Yannick Kirchhoff, Klaus Maier-Hein

[Universitat de Girona, Catalonia, Spain]

Rachika E. Hamadache, Cansu Yalcin, Adrià Casamitjana, Xavier Lladó

[Charité Lab for Artificial Intelligence in Medicine (CLAIM), Germany]

Orhun Utku Aydin, Adam Hilbert, Dietmar Frey

[Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China]

Minghui Zhang, Yun Gu

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Kaiyuan Yang (kaiyuan.yang@uzh.ch) and Pengcheng Shi (shipc1220@gmail.com)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

TopBrain 2025 website: topbrain2025.grand-challenge.org (to appear)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Participants are allowed to use any other public datasets and private in-house data, or modify the supplied training data, provided that they disclose any additional or modified training datasets in their description of the submitted algorithm.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Members of the organizers research groups can participate, and their results can be included in the publications and the leaderboard (as baseline algorithms). However, they are not eligible for awards. People not from the organizers research groups, i.e. from other labs/departments, may participate and are eligible for the awards and to be listed in the leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Top three teams for either MRA or CTA track will be publicly named as shown on the grand-challenge leaderboard webpage, and given a small Swiss wooden goat toy (or some similar toy) as a souvenir at the in-person challenge event. There will be no monetary awards given.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top performing submissions are announced at the in-person challenge event. However, the participating team can choose whether their results will be made public any time before the day of announcement. The top 3-5 teams will be invited to prepare a 5-10 minute presentation for the challenge session to present and discuss their methods.

After the public announcement, a detailed analysis of the submitted results will be available upon request.

If a participant wishes to retract their submission after results are made public, their submitted performance will either be reported in an anonymized fashion, both online and in the publication, or removed from the leaderboard and publication.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The TopBrain challenge results and benchmark will be summarized and published in a journal manuscript. All participants with a reasonable submission are invited to contribute to our challenge publication. Each submission can have maximum three co-authors for the challenge paper. Additional authors from the submissions can be included upon request with justification according to the ICMJE authorship guidelines.

Participating teams may publish their own results separately without any publication embargo.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submission for evaluation will be done on the test datasets via submitted docker containers, i.e. type 2 submissions on Grand Challenge. Participants submit docker containers which are evaluated by organizers on grand-challenge.org on the test set (private test data and annotations).

Along with the docker containers, each participating team is encouraged to submit a 1-page summary describing their methods and approaches one week after the docker submission deadline. This summary is required for co-authorship in the final challenge journal paper.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will have access to the validation set images but without annotations. Predictions on the validation data can be submitted to grand-challenge.org to get them automatically evaluated. However, in order to prevent overfitting and re-training on the validation set, the number of submissions for the validation set predictions is limited to one submission per team per day. The validation phase is not used for final evaluation, and participants are encouraged to use the validation phase to debug and validate their docker submission workflow.

The final test phases only allow for one submission per team for each phase. Each team is given only one opportunity to upload their containers for the hidden test set for a task in a track. In case of technical issues, we allow the participants to try again their docker submissions.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)

- the release date(s) of the results

Preliminary Schedule:

- Challenge Website Online: April 15, 2025
- Release of Annotations for TopBrain Data: July 05, 2025
- Submit to validation phases: August 15 – September 05, 2025
- Submit to final test phases: August 25 – September 05, 2025
- Contacting top performing teams and plan for the in-person session: Aug 10 – Sep 10 2025 (teams that require visas will be contacted earlier. We will coordinate with MICCAI to send invitation letters for visa clearance.)
- in-person challenge event: September 23, 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The image data is reused from TopCoW challenge which has been approved for public release.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Open use. Must provide the source. Use for commercial purposes requires permission of the data owner. (see <https://opendata.swiss/en/terms-of-use>)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Our challenge evaluation will be transparent to all participants similar to the TopCoW challenge. We will set up a GitHub repository to open source, update, and synchronize any changes to the evaluation code for the TopBrain challenge.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The submitted docker containers will be made publicly available with permissions from the participating teams. We encourage the participants to make their code public.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

We will not give monetary awards.

Only the main organizers and their local annotation team will have access to all test and validation labels and the private test datasets.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research,Diagnosis,Education,Screening,Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration

- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort is the general population, as an accurate whole brain vasculature characterization can be beneficial in many clinical applications, ranging from screening of patients being at a higher risk of stroke, to improving the clinical management of patients with cerebrovascular diseases.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is the same as the TopCoW challenge. The TopCoW challenge data cohort was composed of patients admitted to the Stroke Center of the University Hospital Zurich (USZ) in 2018 and 2019. The inclusion criteria for the challenge data were: 1) both MRA and CTA scans were available for that patient; 2) at least the MRA or CTA allowed for an assessment of the CoW anatomy. The patients of the challenge cohort were admitted for or recovering from a stroke-related neurological disorder, including ischemic stroke, transient ischemic attack, stroke mimic, retinal infarct or amaurosis fugax, intracerebral hemorrhage, and cerebral sinus vein thrombosis. Most patients have whole brain vessels intact in at least one of the modalities. For the scans with intact vessels, there is no evidence that the brain vessel anatomy of this cohort would differ significantly from the general population. In a few scans that are affected by underlying pathologies, parts of the brain vessels may be blocked, which is useful for training algorithm against false positive predictions.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed tomography Angiography (CTA) and Time of Flight Magnetic Resonance Angiography (TOF-MRA)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No contextual clinical information will be made available due to the requirement for anonymization.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No clinical information about the patient will be made available due to the requirement for anonymization.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Majority of the image data comes from the TopCoW challenge. The dataset consists of brain angiographic CT and MR scans (CTAs and MRAs). The original CTA scans usually cover neck and head regions, and sometimes just the head region. The original MRA scans typically cover the brain region. The MRA is usually a follow-up scan after a previous CTA of the same patient, but the time stamp information will not be made available.

We will have additional training data from public open datasets.

We will have additional hidden test data from another center.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

There are two tracks for the task, one track for CTA modality and one track for MRA modality. The task is to segment the different anatomical components of the whole brain/head vessels:

External carotid artery region:

External carotid artery (ECA), left and right

Maxillary artery (MA), left and right

Middle meningeal artery (MMA), left and right

Superficial temporal artery (STA), left and right

Internal carotid artery region:

Internal carotid artery (ICA), left and right

Ophthalmic artery (OA), left and right

Anterior choroidal artery (AChA), left and right

Circle of Willis region:

Posterior communicating artery (Pcom), left and right

Anterior communicating artery (Acom)

Anterior cerebral artery (ACA) A1+A2, left and right

Posterior cerebral artery (PCA) P1+P2, left and right

Middle cerebral artery (MCA) M1, left and right

Basilar artery (BA)

MCA branches:

Lateral lenticulostriate artery (LLA), left and right

Anterior temporal artery (ATA), left and right

M2, left and right

M3, left and right

M4, left and right

ACA branches:

A3, left and right

A4, left and right

Callosomarginal artery (CMA), left and right

Orbitofrontal artery (OFA), left and right

Frontopolar artery (FPA), left and right

PCA branches:

P3, left and right

Posterior arteries:

Vertebral artery (VA), left and right

Posterior inferior cerebellar artery (PICA), left and right

Anterior inferior cerebellar artery (AICA), left and right

Superior cerebellar artery (SCA), left and right

Veins:

Superior sagittal sinus

Deep cerebral veins

Straight sinus

Transverse sinus

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Majority of the image data comes from the TopCoW challenge. MRA scans were typically acquired by SIEMENS Skyra model or Avanto Fit model, with magnetic field strength of 3 Tesla or 1.5 Tesla, and with TOF-3D mode or TOF-3D multi slab mode. CTA is typically acquired by SIEMENS SOMATOM Definition Flash using Dual Energy (DE).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Majority of the image data comes from the TopCoW challenge. The clinical data was acquired during routine examinations from patients admitted to the University Hospital Zurich. Standard clinical protocols as of 2019 were applied. For CTA, the voxel size was around 0.45 mm in the X-Y dimension, and around 0.7 mm in the Z dimension. For MRA, the voxel size was around 0.3 mm in the X-Y dimension, and around 0.6 mm in the Z dimension.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Majority of the image data will be from the TopCoW challenge, which were acquired from University Hospital Zurich, Switzerland.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Majority of the image data comes from the TopCoW challenge. The data was acquired at the University Hospital of Zurich during routine examinations following standard procedures for MRA and CTA.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case in task-1 is a 3D angiographic imaging scan of a human brain in either CTA or MRA modality. The task is to segment the vessel anatomy of the whole head region for either MRA track or CTA track.

The relevant vessel components of the human brain are annotated voxel-wise, and different vessel segments are labeled with a different voxel value (see section Algorithm Target for the list).

Both training and test cases are fully annotated.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The training data will include 60 patients from TopCoW dataset with both CTA and MRA modalities, plus 20 CTA and 20 MRA from other public datasets, in total $80 \times 2 = 160$ scans (both image and annotations released)

Validation set: 5 patients (image released to public but without annotations)

Test set will include 30 patients from the TopCoW hidden testset with both modalities, plus 10 CTA and 10 MRA

from another collaborating center. All testset will be hidden.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Similar number of patients and proportion was used in TopCoW 2023 challenge with positive responses. Thus the number should be reasonable for a fairly performant model while giving sufficient evaluation.

The 20 external cases in the testset will help to evaluate out of distribution performance. The multi-center data in both training and test sets encourage participants to invest in generalizability in their algorithms.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Majority of the image data comes from the TopCoW challenge. The angiography scans were obtained from patients admitted for or recovering from a stroke-related neurological disorder, including ischemic stroke, transient ischemic attack, stroke mimic, retinal infarct or amaurosis fugax, intracerebral hemorrhage, and cerebral sinus vein thrombosis. For stroke patients in our dataset, their MRA imaging data were usually after treatment in case of any occlusion stroke but without visible interventional artifacts. In rare cases, the angiography scans can see the large vessel occlusions in one of the modalities.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

30 testset is a subset of hidden testset from the TopCoW challenge. Additional testset cases from another center will also be hidden. All testset are unpublished and private.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The annotation setup and workflow is similar to the TopCoW challenge. Each case will be annotated by an annotator-approver workflow. The annotations from the TopCoW challenge dataset are kept for the CoW vessels. Remaining vessels of the whole brain will be labeled or verified voxel-wise by the same annotator team from the TopCoW challenge who have been trained on brain vessel anatomy from clinical experts in the organizing team. The cases that annotators are uncertain will be flagged, and sent for further verification and approval by the clinical experts. The clinical expert team is led by clinicians from neurosurgery, neuro-radiology, and neurology. All patients from the TopCoW challenge had both CTA and MRA modalities, with one scan for each modality. Annotators and clinical experts have both CTA and MRA modalities available to annotate and verify. The anatomy of the brain vessels will be first inspected in both CTA and MRA to diagnose the anatomical components. Then the brain vessels will be annotated for each modality separately. We have one to two primary annotators who manually annotate and correct all the cases. The clinical experts educate and train the primary annotators on the vessels to be labelled and verify any flagged unsure cases. If there are differences in clinical opinions, we collect the responses from clinical experts and let the most experienced clinician make the final decision.

The manual and preliminary annotations will be done by a human-in-the-loop setup. The initial few cases are manually annotated and verified by human raters to train an initial segmentation model. Then the initial model is used to pre-label the next few cases, which are sent for human correction and verification. The model for

pre-labeling is then iteratively upgraded and improved with incoming new verified annotations. All annotated cases will be manually verified and approved by at least one human rater.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotation setup and workflow is similar to the TopCoW challenge. The annotation protocol on how to segment vessel components were discussed and agreed upon by the clinical experts. The cases that annotators are uncertain are flagged, and sent for further verification and approval by the clinical experts. The manual annotation and verification are done in 3D using virtual-reality (VR) for efficient diagnosis and visualization.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Annotations are verified and approved by a team of clinical experts on neurovascular disease. Our clinical team is led by neurologists, neuro-radiologists, and neuro-surgeons specializing in neuro-vascular diseases.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N.A.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same data used as TopCoW challenge. The data were anonymized (removal and anonymization of relevant DICOM patient information). Additional de-facing and cropping procedures were performed to ensure patient privacy in the image data after converting the DICOM to NIfTI format. The defaced image includes only the braincase region. Other than the defacing and the cropping to braincase region steps, no further preprocessing of the data is performed to keep the data as close to the clinical setting as possible. The image data are saved in NIfTI format, 16-bit signed, and in LPS+ orientation.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We analyzed the inter-rater agreement in terms of voxel-wise annotations of individual CoW components after the CoW variant had been diagnosed and verified by the clinicians. The agreement was 90% class-average Dice score, 99% cIDice score, and near 0 class-average zero-th Betti number error. Recently we also conducted inter-rater agreement for CoW variant diagnosis with a senior neurosurgeon and the agreement was also high. The annotations of TopCoW have been downloaded and viewed by hundreds of participants, including neuro-radiologists and neurosurgeons as participants. The feedback on the annotation quality has been very positive. Thus we believe the annotation workflow and setup of TopCoW produce clinically approved and high-quality annotations, which can ensure the same high-quality for TopBrain challenge.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

MRA might amplify the effect of stenosis in vessels. Both CTA and MRA modalities might contain common artifacts such as flow-dependent signal cancellation artifacts, noise artifacts, ringing artifacts, pulsation artifacts, and beam hardening artifacts. These artifacts might cause the vessels to be over- or under-segmented, and might affect the vessel anatomy diagnosis.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The assessment is by the following metrics:

1. Class-average Dice similarity coefficient
2. Centerline Dice (cIDice)
3. Class-average zero-th Betti number errors
4. Class-average Hausdorff Distance 95% Percentile (HD95)

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Dice similarity coefficient and centerline-Dice [Shit et al. 2021] measure the voxel overlap between the ground truth and the segmentation prediction. In particular, we highlight the centerline-Dice metric (cIDice), which is suitable for evaluating voxel-wise overlap for tubular and curvilinear structures such as CoW vessels [Maier-Hein et al. 2022]. cIDice extends the traditional Dice by also measuring how much of the vessels are covered (coverage of vessel network).

Betti numbers measure the topological properties such as connected components and circular holes.

Some of the vessel components are smaller in diameter and volume, which are not best evaluated in overlap-based metrics like Dice and cIDice scores as they are sensitive to small disagreement in voxels (Reinke et al., 2021). Thus, we introduce boundary-based metrics like Hausdorff distance to better evaluate vessel components with smaller structure size. 95% percentile Hausdorff distance (HD95) is less affected by extreme outliers.

References:

- Maier-Hein, Lena, et al. "Metrics reloaded: Pitfalls and recommendations for image analysis validation." ArXiv preprint arXiv:2206.01653 (2022).
- Reinke, A., Tizabi, M.D., Sudre, C.H., Eisenmann, M., Radsch, T., Baumgartner, M., Acion, L., Antonelli, M., Arbel, T., Bakas, S., et al., 2021. Common limitations of image processing metrics: A picture story. arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.05642 .
- Shit, Suprosanna, et al. "cIDice-a novel topology-preserving loss function for tubular structure segmentation." Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. 2021.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking for the awards of the MICCAI event will be based on the leaderboards displayed on grand-challenge website, which rank the teams by the descending order of their per-case performance on each metric. The leaderboard uses equal weights for each metric column and used the mean of the positions or ranks from metric columns, or rank-then-average.

After the challenge submissions, we will perform additional ranking using Wilcoxon signed-rank test (with greater or lesser hypothesis as appropriate to the metric) on the test set to rank the submitted methods for each metric. Similarly, we will then use equal weights for each metric ranking, and use the mean of the ranks, or rank-then-average.

Bootstrapping (sampling with replacement) may also be performed on the test-set to analyze ranking robustness and stability post-challenge. The bootstrapped ranking for each metric is obtained via Wilcoxon signed-rank test (with greater or lesser hypothesis as appropriate to the metric) on the test set.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For missing results on test cases, i.e. a false positive or a false negative predicted vessel anatomical component, the evaluations for Dice, cIDice will be 0. The Betti number error will not be affected by missing results. Boundary based metrics like Hausdorff distance will be set to the most penalizing value of the average dimension of the human head region for missing results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Wilcoxon signed-rank test (with greater or lesser hypothesis as appropriate to the metric) indicates if there is any statistical significance on the test data between two teams being compared. Similar ranking schemes were used in other recent medical challenges like BraTS challenge (<http://braintumorsegmentation.org/>) and VerSe challenge (<https://verse2020.grand-challenge.org/>), and also as recommended by the literature [Maier-Hein et al. 2018].

References:

Maier-Hein, Lena, et al. "Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care." *Nature communications* 9.1 (2018): 1-13.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Each team will be compared with the other teams using Wilcoxon signed-rank test to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between the two compared teams.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Similar statistical methods were used in other challenges such as BraTS challenge (<http://braintumorsegmentation.org/>) and VerSe challenge (<https://verse2020.grand-challenge.org/>) with positive feedback from the participants, and as recommended by the literature [Maier-Hein et al. 2018].

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In the final publication, we will carry out additional topological analysis on methods that can perform well for volumetric metrics while preserving topological and geometric properties.

The resulting summary publication may conduct a post-challenge ranking that considers more properties to re-rank the submissions. We may request winning teams that may be performant due to additional datasets to conduct ablation studies to analyze the contributions from additional datasets. And we may have additional post-challenge rankings that such teams use their methods to retrain on our smaller released dataset and compare the performance.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A